

A Study on the Influence of Financial Debt on Individuals in the region of UT of DNH & DD

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Abstract - Invention of credit that gives birth to a debt has played the salient role in modern economics. Debt is used by the units in economics to fund their economic activity, that might not be possible only relying on cash. Thus, debt has become an important aspect in present day economics. However, the use of debt should be judicious. Debt is a financial arrangement for a specific period of time with an add-on payback, and if the same isn't paid back in time it's no good to the economy as well as the one taking debt. Such a situation called as debt trap may influence debt holder adversely. This paper attempts to study such influence on the individuals that hold or might have hold the debt. Empirical data was collected through as structured questionnaire and analysed to gather the insights on said subject. The data analysed for various constructs such as; Stress Level, Mental Health, Physical Health, Relation with Family & Friends, Job Performance, and Overall Quality of Life, it was found that majority of the respondents were neutral on all the examined constructs except for 'Mental Health'. It was found that majority of the respondents were moderately affected on their 'Mental Health' due to financial debt taken by them. This paper contributes to the existing knowledge of individual behavioural finance with fresh evidence from the region of Union Territory of Dadra and Nagar Haveli & Daman and Diu, India.

Key Words: Individual Debt, Financial Debt, Financial Wellbeing, Debt, Individual Behavioural Finance.

INTRODUCTION

Debt is referred to as an obligation. It is generally associated to finance, where one is obliged to pay back in return to consumption of goods or/and services. Debt can be created in organized as well as unorganized manner. For instance, if an individual has borrowed a sum of money from a relative or a friend, one has created the debt in an unorganized manner. While an individual taking loan, using credit card, or enjoying any sort of deferred payment options from an incorporated financial institution it is debt created in organized manner.

While debt is a viable source of finance, it should be use with a caution. Sometimes people do not make a thoughtful decision while raising or creating a debt. The debt that is not created thoughtfully ends up as a burden in future. For example, Mr. X needed urgent funds. He takes the personal loan from ABC Bank Ltd., at say 15% per annum for 5 years. Initially, he could manage to pay the EMI's on time, however after six months due to increase in his household expenditure he found it difficult to pay back the debt. Thus, in this

example Mr. X did not consider the rise in household expenditure in future. This ultimately will create a burden for Mr. X and consequently, may impact his personal and financial well-being. So, using debt for various reasons may appear viable however it may turn into non-viable in future due to numerous reasons. In present study the researchers aim is to examine the influence of financial debt on individuals.

The philosophy of this research is interpretivism. With an approach of deduction, the researchers aim was to interpret the empirical evidence gathered for said research phenomenon. To study the concept, existing literature was explored while as mentioned earlier the aim of this study is to describe the empirical evidence. Therefore, the type of research this study is "exploratory and descriptive". Primary data was collected using google forms. The sampling technique adopted was non-probability, convenience, and snow-balling techniques. The participants of this study were from the region of UT of Dadra and Nagar Haveli and Daman and Diu (UT of DNH & DD). The data collected is analyzed using descriptive statistics.

The literature reviewed is discussed as follows:

- **Student Debt and Financial Well-being:** Debt negatively impacts financial well-being, particularly when it finances children's education rather than borrowers' or their spouses'. (Korankye & Kalenkoski)
- **Attitude Towards Debt Management and Financial Behaviours:** A positive approach to debt management enhances financial well-being, while compulsive buying behavior detracts from it. Work experience and income play significant roles in fostering financial confidence. (Kuknor & Sharma)
- **Financial Literacy and Debt in Malaysia:** Financial literacy and demographic factors like age significantly influence financial well-being. High debt levels were observed among respondents, emphasizing the need for education on managing finances effectively. (Muhamad & Norwani)
- **Types of Debt in Switzerland:** Payment arrears reduce financial and life satisfaction more than other types of debt. Demographic factors like citizenship and income can mitigate the negative impact. (Coste, Henchoz, & Wernli)
- **Young Adults and Debt:** Student loans lead to financial stress despite enabling family support and social

activities. Self-esteem positively correlates with subjective well-being. (Fan & Ryu)

- **Indian Socioeconomic Groups and COVID-19:** Income, education, financial literacy, and access to financial services significantly affect financial well-being. The pandemic exacerbated financial struggles for households and businesses. (Shedge & Joshi)
- **Debt and Health in Spain:** Non-mortgage debt payments and arrears adversely affect health outcomes, while mortgage payments do not. Long-term economic stability is critical for better health. (BLÁZQUEZ & BUDRIA)
- **Young Adults’ Mental Health:** Revolving debt negatively impacts mental health, while perceived financial capabilities have a positive effect. (Jinhee Kim & Chatterjeeb)
- **Financial Conditions and Health:** Favorable financial conditions improve physical and mental health, while financial distress increases the risk of depression. (Bialowolski et al.)
- **Financial Well-being Framework:** Socio-economic factors and financial socialization drive healthy financial behaviours and overall financial well-being. (Kaur, Singh, & Gupta)

The objectives set for this study were:

- **To identify the usage of debt by the individuals in the region of UT of DNH & DD.**
- **To study the influence of debt on the individuals’ various aspects of life.**
- **To study the influence of debt on the individuals’ financial wellbeing.**

DATA ANALYSIS

Out of the 142 people surveyed, 81% are male (115), 18% are female (25), and just 1 person (1%) identifies as “Other.” This clearly shows that men make up the majority of the respondents, which could mean that discussions or experiences around financial debt are more common or accessible for men in this region. The age group 35-44 years forms the largest proportion, contributing 30% (43) of the total respondents. This suggests that individuals in their mid-career phase are most actively involved in financial debt. The 55-64 years group at 4% (6) and the 65+ group at 1% (1) indicate minimal involvement with financial debt, possibly reflecting retirement and reduced borrowing needs.

Full-time employees form the largest group (44% of total respondents), with a notable concentration in the ₹2,00,000-

₹4,99,999 income bracket (67%). This suggests that individuals with stable employment and mid-range incomes are more likely to engage with financial debt. Self-employed individuals make up 22% of the total sample, with a significant proportion earning between ₹5,00,000 and ₹9,99,999, highlighting their potential financial independence and greater borrowing capacity. Students comprise 13% of the respondents, with the majority falling under the “Under ₹2,00,000” category, reflecting limited financial resources and higher dependency on external funding. Part-time employees (11%) and retirees (6%) show a more balanced income distribution, though their lower income levels likely influence their debt involvement. Unemployed individuals (3%) and entrepreneurs (1%) represent the smallest segments, indicating minimal engagement with financial debt, possibly due to income instability or alternative financial support systems.

92% (130 respondents) reported having financial debt, indicating a high prevalence of borrowing across various demographic groups. Only 8% (11 respondents) stated they have no debt, suggesting that a very small portion of the population surveyed manages to avoid financial obligations.

A. Usage of debt by the individuals in the region of UT of DNH & DD

Personal loans (34%) are the most common form of debt, highlighting widespread reliance on unsecured borrowing for personal expenses. Utilities-related debt, including bills like electricity and cellular services, accounts for 21%, suggesting challenges in managing regular household expenses. Student loans and credit card debt each make up 15%, reflecting the dual pressures of educational financing and consumer credit. Vehicle loans represent 11%, indicating investment in personal transportation. The total reported instances of debt types (201) indicate that many respondents likely hold multiple forms of debt simultaneously. Business loans (3%) and property loans (3%) show limited engagement in entrepreneurial and asset-based borrowing.

Table 1 – Distribution of Financial Debt taken by the respondents.

Financial Debt	% age
Auto Loans	13.46%
Business	3.85%
Cellular bills	0.96%
Credit card debt	25.00%
Medical Bills	6.73%
Mortgage	11.54%
Personal loans	34.62%
Property Loan	0.96%
Student loans	1.92%
Two-wheeler loan	0.96%

The data on the number of debts highlight that 39% of individuals manage two different forms of debt and 25% juggle three debts reflects the complexity of their financial commitments. Meanwhile, 4% of respondents handle four

separate debts. This emphasizes the importance of effective debt management strategies and accessible financial advisory services.

A significant portion of respondents (27%) have debt exposure between ₹5,00,000 and ₹9,99,999, indicating a relatively high level of financial obligation among a substantial group. 25% of individuals reported debt exposure under ₹1,00,000, showing a considerable number managing smaller-scale debts. 23% fall within the ₹10,00,000-₹24,99,999 range, highlighting a notable segment with substantial debt commitments. 18% have debt exposure between ₹1,00,000 and ₹4,99,999, reflecting mid-level borrowing activity. High-value debt is less common, with only 5% reporting debt above ₹50,00,000 and 1% falling in the ₹25,00,000-₹49,99,999 category.

B. Influence of Financial Debt on an Individual

The analysis highlights that stress and anxiety are the most prevalent psychological effects of financial debt, reported more frequently than physical or mental health issues. While a proportion of individuals remain largely unaffected, a notable segment consistently experiences adverse effects across these categories. This underscores the critical need for effective debt management strategies and robust mental health support systems.

- **Stress/Anxiety:** A significant 30% of respondents report sometimes experiencing stress or anxiety related to financial debt, representing the most commonly reported frequency. 23% of individuals rarely encounter such stress, while 22% consistently experience anxiety. A smaller segment, 13%, never faces these issues, and 12% often report stress or anxiety.
- **Impact on Physical Health:** 27% of respondents report never experiencing physical health impacts due to financial debt, the highest proportion within this category. 24% sometimes feel physical health effects, while 18% always experience such impacts. 18% rarely face physical health issues, and 13% often report being affected.
- **Impact on Mental Health:** Both the 'Never' and 'Rarely' categories each account for 24% of

respondents, indicating a balanced distribution of those less affected. 18% of individuals consistently experience mental health challenges due to debt. 17% of respondents report sometimes or often facing mental health impacts.

Debt’s influence on various life aspects—stress levels, mental health, physical health, relationships with family and friends, job performance, and overall quality of life—shows some clear patterns:

- **Stress Level:** 23 respondents (16%) reported a major impact, while 37 (26%) experienced a moderate impact. A significant 41 respondents (29%) remained neutral.
- **Mental Health:** 14 respondents (10%) reported a major impact, and 39 (28%) felt a moderate impact. A higher proportion, 37 respondents (26%), stayed neutral.
- **Physical Health:** 16 respondents (11%) reported a major impact, with 25 (18%) indicating a moderate impact. The highest percentage, 43 respondents (30%), remained neutral.
- **Relationships with Family & Friends:** 12 respondents (9%) reported a major impact, and 35 (25%) experienced a moderate impact. A large 42 respondents (30%) reported a neutral effect.
- **Job Performance:** 12 respondents (9%) reported a major impact, while 38 (27%) faced a moderate impact. Neutral responses accounted for 40 respondents (28%).
- **Overall Quality of Life:** 20 respondents (14%) reported a major impact, and 35 (25%) experienced a moderate impact. The most common response, 48 respondents (34%), was neutral.

- **Ability to Pay Monthly Bills:** 26 respondents (18%) reported being extremely affected, 17 respondents (12%) significantly affected, 45 respondents (32%) moderately affected, 40 respondents (28%) slightly affected, and 13 respondents (9%) not affected at all.

- **Use of Credit for Essential Expenses:** 11 respondents (8%) reported extreme reliance on credit, 30 respondents (21%) significantly reliant, 28 respondents (20%) moderately reliant, 49 respondents (35%) slightly reliant, and 23 respondents (16%) not reliant on credit for essential needs.

- **Overall Financial Wellbeing:** 19 respondents (13%) reported extreme impact on their financial well-being, 20 respondents (14%) significant impact, 35 respondents (25%) moderate impact, 48 respondents (34%) slight impact, and 19 respondents (14%) no impact at all.

DISCUSSION

55 respondents (39%) reported seeking help, demonstrating awareness of support systems. 86 respondents (61%) had not sought any form of financial counselling, indicating a potential gap in financial literacy or accessibility to such services.

Effectiveness of Financial Counselling or Debt Management Services Analysis: Positive Impact: 64% of respondents found financial counseling or debt management services helpful. Moderate Helpfulness: 33% rated the services as moderately helpful, indicating some benefit but room for improvement. Limited Effectiveness: 25% reported only slight improvements in their financial situation. Ineffectiveness: 11% found the services not helpful at all.

- **Debt Distribution:** A large number of respondents (27%) carry debts between ₹5,00,000 and ₹9,99,999, indicating a significant financial burden for many. Meanwhile, 25% manage smaller-scale debts below ₹1,00,000, and only 6% report debts above ₹25,00,000.

- **Demographic Insights:** Debt is most prevalent among individuals aged 25-44, likely due to work and family responsibilities. Participation from those 55 and above is much lower, suggesting greater financial stability in later years.

- **Gender Representation:** Men show higher involvement in financial debt, especially in the 25-44 age group. Notably, the “Other” gender category had minimal representation, pointing to the need for more inclusive research.

- **Financial Counselling Effectiveness:** Of those who sought financial counseling (39% of respondents), 64% found the services helpful to varying degrees. However, 11% found them ineffective, and 25% reported only slight benefit, suggesting room for improvement in these services.

- **Impact on Financial Wellbeing:** Monthly Bill Payments: 62% reported being affected in their ability to pay monthly bills, with 18% extremely impacted. Reliance on Credit: 64% use credit for essential expenses to some extent, with 8% relying on it heavily. Overall Financial Well-being: 52% of respondents reported at least moderate impact on their overall financial well-being due to debt, while only 14% felt no impact.

- **Need for Financial Literacy:** These findings highlight the need for more accessible and effective financial literacy programs and enhanced debt management support, especially for younger and mid-career individuals managing substantial financial obligations.

CONCLUSIONS

The study on the influence of financial debt on individuals in the Union Territory of Dadra and Nagar Haveli & Daman and Diu (UT of DNH & DD) provides significant insights into how financial obligations impact various aspects of life. The findings highlight that while many respondents remain neutral about debt’s influence on their stress levels, physical health, job performance, and quality of life, a notable proportion experience moderate to severe impacts on their mental health. This underscores the psychological burden associated with financial debt, which can lead to long-term well-being issues if not managed effectively.

Furthermore, the high reliance on personal loans and credit card debt reflects a dependence on unsecured borrowing, often leading to financial strain. The data also shows a significant number of individuals managing multiple debts, which amplifies their financial burden and complicates their ability

to meet monthly expenses. The limited use of financial counselling services, despite their perceived helpfulness, suggests a gap in financial literacy and awareness about available support systems.

Overall, this research contributes to the growing body of knowledge on individual behavioral finance, providing fresh evidence from the region. It emphasizes the need for effective debt management strategies and robust financial education to mitigate the adverse effects of debt on mental health and overall financial well-being.

REFERENCES

1. Bialowolski, P., Weziak-Bialowolska, D., b, a. T., Chen, Y., VanderWeele, T. J., & McNeely, E. (2021). The role of financial conditions for physical and mental health. Evidence from a longitudinal survey and insurance claims data. *Social Science & Medicine* 281.
2. BLÁZQUEZ, M., & BUDRIA, S. (2018). The Effects of Over-indebtedness on Individual Health. *REVIEW OF PUBLIC ECONOMICS*.
3. Coste, T., Henchoz, C., & Wernli, B. (2020). Debt and Subjective Well-Being: Does the Type of Debt Matter? *Swiss Journal of Sociology* ; 46(3), 445-465.
4. Fan, L., & Ryu, S. (September 2023). Financial debts and subjective well-being of young adults: An adaption of the stress process model. *Journal of Consumer Affairs* published by Wiley Periodicals.
5. Jinhee Kim, a., & Chatterjeeb, S. (2021). Financial Debt and Mental Health of Young Adults. *Journal of Financial Counseling and Planning*, Volume 32, Number 2, 187-201.
6. Kaur, G., Singh, M., & Gupta, S. (2022). Analysis of key factors influencing individual financial well-being using ISM and MICMAC approach.
7. Korankye, T., & Charlene M. Kalenkoski. (Written : May 20, 2021; posted: 4 Apr 2022). Student Loan Debt and Financial Well-Being of the Borrower: Does It Matter Whom the Debt Is For? *Journal of Personal Finance*, 16 Pages.
8. Kuknor, S., & Sharma, A. (October-December 2017). The Relationship of Debt Management, Compulsive Buying Behavior and Financial Well-Being ; Vol.8, No. 4. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*, .
9. Muhamad, N. A., & Norwani, N. M. (June 2019). THE INFLUENCE OF FINANCIAL LITERACY, DEBT AND DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS ON FINANCIAL WELL-BEING. *International Journal of Contemporary Applied Researches* Vol. 6, No. 6.
10. Shedje, M. R., & Joshi, D. S. (2023). Financial Wellbeing of Individuals in India *Eur. Eur. Chem. Bull.* 12(Special issue 8), 4740-4753.